

PREVENTION OF HUMAN PARASITIC DISEASES

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Abstract: The article presents data on infection with parasitic diseases of people, transmission routes and disease prevention, treatment.

Keywords : parasitic disease, cases of giardiasis, ascariasis, trichocephalosis, enterobiosis, hymenolepidosis, diphyllbothriosis, opisthorchiasis, clonorhosis, toxocarosis, teniarinchiasis are registered annually.

According to WHO, more than 4.5 billion people are infected with parasitic diseases in the world. human. The average incidence of the world's population is 100 million per year. During life, almost every person suffers from a parasitic disease, cases of giardiasis, ascariasis, trichocephalosis, enterobiosis, hymenolepidosis, diphyllbothriosis, opisthorchiasis, clonorhosis, toxocarosis, teniarinchiasis are registered annually.

These are parasites - they do not choose their age, they cause great damage to the health of a person of any age. The word parasite has Greek roots and in translation means "freeloader", "parasite". A parasite is an organism that uses an individual of another species (host) as a food source and habitat. The parasite and the host are in an antagonistic relationship.

Parasitic diseases can be caused by both pathogenic bacteria and parasitic protozoa, parasitic arthropods, viruses, parasitic worms. Parasites, both in humans and animals, can infect any part of the body, even the eyes and brain.

To prevent parasitic diseases, first of all, everyone should know the ways of infection with them, the following ways of infection with parasites have been studied in science; the first way of infection is food, or alimentary (dysentery amoeba, giardia, echinococcus) - ingestion with food and water, through the digestive tract with unwashed vegetables, fruits, berries, poorly fried meat and fish, through contaminated water or soil, contact with animals (for example: 1 g of cat feces contains up to 20 million toxoplasma cysts; echinococcosis is transmitted with fur products), if sanitary and hygienic rules are not observed (both the population and sellers, food industry and catering workers). Often,

eggs of several types of helminths can be found on one loaf of bread from a street tent.

The second way of infection is air-dust (pinworm eggs, dwarf tapeworm) - ingestion with dust when breathing. When inhaling dust with eggs or parasite cysts. The third way is percutaneous - active penetration through the skin (hookworm, schistosoma). Parasites can actively drill through the integuments and are introduced through them. So, the larvae of schistosomes, piercing the skin, enter the human body while bathing in freshwater reservoirs. The fourth way is transovarial and transplacental: transmission to offspring through an egg or placenta (toxoplasma, malarial plasmodium). The fifth way of infection is sexual (vaginal trichomonas): during sexual intercourse. The sixth way is transmissible: with bites of blood-sucking insects and ticks through the blood (leishmania, trypanosoma, tick-borne encephalitis viruses). Mosquitoes are carriers of malaria, filariasis and other parasites. The seventh way is contact and household (itchy itch, enterobiosis): when contacting the patient or his belongings.

One thing to remember is that most parasitic diseases are asymptomatic or under the "mask" of other diseases. For example, children are often unsuccessfully treated for allergies or atopic dermatitis, and the cure comes only after anthelmintic therapy. But even for adults, a long absence of treatment is not safe, a wide variety of complications are possible, up to the development of tumors.

People do not realize the fact that the symptoms of sluggish parasitic diseases are nonspecific. And most turn to non-core specialists: an allergist, gastroenterologist or dermatologist, depending on the leading symptoms of the disease. As a result, a person is treated for years, unaware of the true cause of his illness. Parasitic diseases cause a delay in the mental and physical development of children, cause allergization of the body of the affected person, reduce resistance to infectious and somatic diseases, reduce the effectiveness of vaccination.

The use of high-tech diagnostic methods makes it possible to identify parasitic diseases even in the absence of symptoms. Prevention of parasitic diseases is very simple, it is necessary to observe sanitary and hygienic rules, at home, buying food products, it is also necessary to pay great attention to the purchase of clothes, because when trying on, you need to be sure that no one has tried it on before you. This is a way of transmitting skin parasites. Wash your hands often, as public transport is a hotbed of infection with giardiasis.

Now all over the world there are methods for determining the parasite of a human, for example; determination of worm eggs, helminth eggs, pinworm eggs, enterobiasis, spatula Anti-Echinococcus-IgG, IgG class antibodies to echinococcus antigens, anti-E. granulosus, antibodies to giardia antigens total IgA, IgM, IgG-anti-Lambliа intestinalis IgA, IgM, IgG total; anti-Giardia Lambliа IgA, IgM.

Medicine is developing year after year, and the types of various human parasites are also increasing at the same time. The best method of prevention is the observance of personal hygiene, timely access to medical personnel and love your health.

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